

#12

Evaluation & Impact Assessment **ACTIONS: IDENTIFICATION, PROOF, PHASE**

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>INTERROGATING ADDRESSING APPLYING EVALUATION & IMPACT ASSESSMENT</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>At decision-making junctures where actions for a project/initiative to take are identified. This can be at the project/initiative planning stage, or later in the project/initiative (if there is scope to decide actions).</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Small to medium (max 20), although use of the tool could be replicated in smaller groups (of a large consortium) and merged.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>No technical skills required for use of the tool itself, although the knowledge introduced by the external expert may be new and challenging.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>1-3 hours (depending on the length of associated discussions & the number of actions being decided on).</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>Requires basic materials, little or no cost.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools # 8, 22, 24, 25.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source: Teagasc

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- Use all the knowledge available in a multi-actor project/initiative to brainstorm potential actions for the project/initiative to take.
- Involve an outside 'expert/s' to evaluate the chosen actions and to suggest more/alternative potential actions.
- Make decisions in selecting actions, plotting them on a 'stairs chart'
- Use the stairs chart to periodically appraise progress in implementing actions, revising the actions/their timing where necessary.

Background and Logic

A principal advantage of interactive innovation in a multi-actor group is that it leverages the different knowledges/ perspectives etc. of all actors involved. It is particularly vital that a rigorous multi-actor approach is taken at junctures where decisions are taken in relation to what actions a project/initiative will take. These decisions – regarding actions – decide the fate of how effective/ innovative a project/initiative will ultimately be.

This tool¹ employs a method to support all actors to influence the decision-making process in relation to actions that a project/initiative will take. It involves engaging an external actor/s into the process, as a neutral commentator regarding the choice of actions, and also to possibly challenge the group by introducing new/ alternative actions. A multi-actor panel of experts can also be convened. Actions are chosen by the group and plotted on a 'stairs chart'. The stairs chart is subsequently used to assess progress in implementing actions. The chart can be reflexively adapted to accommodate new actions and/or to revise planned actions. The tool can be used to plan actions for a whole project or for a single work package, as required by the particular project/ initiative in which it is being used.

Materials

- Thick black markers
- Sticky-notes
- Pens
- Stairs diagram, either printed in large poster size or drawn on flipchart paper or a whiteboard.
- Camera/phone camera.

¹ This tool is adapted from [Macken-Walsh et al., 2019](#)

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

Step 1: Preparation

- Explain the purpose, logic and background.
- Show the multi-actor animation (optional) to remind participants how vital different forms of knowledge are for interactive innovation.

Step 2: Brainstorm Actions

- It may be conducive to the decision-making process to undertake a field visit that relates to the decision-making process concerning actions. For example, a field visit to a site that relates to or is similar to the area/topic in relation to which the decision-making process is focused. Having a simple Walk About (with or without a host) will sensitise participants to the decision-making matter/s and is likely to provoke ideas.
- After the field visit, participants take a seat around a table with an appropriate topic banner relating to the decision-making topic. To engender a sense of collective ownership of the decision-making process, the topic banner can begin with 'Us and... (topic)'.
- Issue sticky notes and black markers to participants – preferably different colour sticky notes to different actor types, so that their contributions are identifiable (this may not be possible if there is a relatively large group – however it is possible also to place identifying stamps or stickers on sticky notes in advance).
- Ask participants to discuss what actions are appropriate to take, considering criteria such as the following (*which may be adapted /replaced as needed* – the aim of this particular exercise is to avoid entirely aspirational actions and instead focus on those that are reasonably implementable):
 - » Cost-effective? (considering any budgetary limitations)
 - » Impactful ('reasonable' expected benefit/s for 'reasonable' investment)
 - » Achievable (considering any time constraints, available human resources, any other factor, such as geographical factors etc.)
- Ask participants to consider these (or adapted/customised) criteria and note their suggested actions on sticky notes (providing assistance where needed).
- There is no need to 'proof' the actions at this point – this is a brainstorming process where all suggestions are valuable.

- The output of Step 2 is a diverse range of actions produced by all actors of a multi-actor group.
- Photograph actions for future reference.

Step 3: Shortlist & Proof Actions

- The invited expert/s may enter the workshop at this point, perhaps just after a short break for participants. S/he is / they are introduced by the facilitator. It may be the case that participants nominated the particular expert/s or perhaps s/he has been selected by the facilitator. It is possible (and desirable, where possible) to have a (multi-actor) panel of external experts.
- Present the stairs chart to participants & ask them to identify – from the sticky notes on the table - any imminent/'easy win'/flagship actions to be taken (the stairs chart can be customised by entering dates in days/months/quarters/years etc.).
- Each action is discussed:
 - » Does everyone agree that this action should be taken (and at this time etc., if relevant), and considering the criteria (Step 2), is it a valuable and possible action to take?
 - » Are there any other actions that could be taken instead of this one, or with it? (again, drawing from sticky notes on the table)
 - » Then, ask the visiting expert if there are other possible actions that the group may wish to consider?
 - » If the expert has an alternative/added action and the group agrees with it, it can be added to the stairs chart or, instead, added to the table for future consideration.
 - » The process (above) continues until the group has identified a sufficient range of actions.
 - » It is important that the actions chosen don't all come from one or two actor types – this will be easily visible if actor types use different colour/differentiated sticky notes in Step 2. If one or two actor types are represented by the majority of actions selected repeatedly, the facilitator can address this by asking participants to examine the wider range of sticky notes.
- The output of Step 3 is an agreed set of proofed actions, which have been informed (where valued by participants) by an outside expert/s.

Step 4: Use of Agreed Actions for Evaluation

- The involvement of all the diverse actors in the multi-actor group in both identifying and selecting actions can be verified by using differentiated sticky notes.
- The involvement of the external expert/s provides for neutral appraisal of the content of the actions, according to state-of-the-art and with a viewpoint that is outside of the immediate project/initiative team. A (multi-actor) panel of diverse experts can provide diversity in the appraisal process. This 'peer review' type process brings new expertise & rigour and can give confidence to project/initiative partners that their chosen actions are the best possible available. However, it is also the case that a balance has to be struck between internal (project/initiative) 'experts' and external 'experts'. Insider knowledge of internal participants is highly valuable, and in the steps above, they are positioned as empowered interrogators and judges of external viewpoints.

- The proofed set of actions (placed on a phased timeline) represent a blueprint against which progress can be periodically assessed. However, as innovation processes are continuously evolving and changing direction, new/adapted actions may be identified. This process should be accommodated by repeated use of the tool as necessary.

